

**A COMBINATION OF TRADITIONAL AND INNOVATIVE APPROACHES IN
TEACHING ENGLISH STUDENTS OF TECHNICAL FIELDS**

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Abstract:

This article discusses the features of teaching English to students of technical specialties. In particular, the analysis of the possibilities of using both traditional (grammar-translation) and innovative methods (project training, debates, case studies) is carried out. The authors consider the effectiveness of using various methods at different stages of learning English, and also assesses the effectiveness of learning using these methods. An in-depth analysis of the peculiarities of teaching English in technical universities proves the importance of combining traditional and new teaching methods.

Key words: English for technical specialties, grammar-translation method, project method, debate method, case study method.

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Introduction

The intensive process of transition to the information society is associated with the widespread introduction of new information technologies and computer means of telecommunications. It necessitates the development of new forms and methods of teaching foreign languages. Linguistic research is a complex and multidimensional process based on interdisciplinary approaches, which are analyzed from the standpoint of both teaching methods, new information technologies, and language specifics. In the Russian methodology of teaching foreign languages, a system of training future specialists in professional communication in a foreign language is being developed. A number of authors such as T.S. Ruzhentseva [1], N.V. Yankina [2], I.A. Raskhodova [3], N.G. Alyavdina [4] and others studied this problem. The relevance of the research is due to the need to develop new modern approaches in teaching foreign languages in accordance with existing educational standards.

In modern realities, knowledge of foreign languages is one of the key requirements for a specialist in the labor market. The requirements for graduates of technical fields are similar. However, unlike other areas, the teaching methodology is based on the grammar-translation method. The reason for this is a number of

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qualification requirements for proficiency in written English (reading foreign literature, correspondence with colleagues abroad, self-presentation).

Along with the requirements for training specialists, there is a specific contingent of students. According to long-term observations, students of technical specialties have a high degree of self-control. Before starting communication in English, the student needs to build the entire phrase in full. In writing, this leads to an increase in the time required to complete the task. Another characteristic feature of students in engineering specialties is a systematic approach. In some cases, this helps to assimilate the material, this is especially noticeable when mastering grammatical topics. However, this may increase the task execution time. It is worth noting the general trend of educational interest of the generation of students born in the 2000s. Young people are characterized by low motivation to study. This is due to the ubiquity of clip-based mass culture, which is characterized by a rapid change of images, constant attraction of attention with new rewards. Accordingly, the educational system must accept this challenge. In this regard, it is worth considering the introduction of innovative educational technologies into the educational process. Thus, in teaching English to students of technical fields, a balanced combination of traditional pedagogical methods (in particular, the grammar-translation method) and new technologies (cases, projects, debates) is of key importance. Let's take a closer look at the use of each of the techniques.

The grammar-translation method is of key importance in the training of technical specialists. Future engineering specialists need a fairly good perception of information on a narrow subject. Technical texts are dominated by special vocabulary (terminology) and certain grammatical constructions (complex subject, complex complement, passive voice, impersonal sentences). Even with excellent conversational skills, it is difficult to understand the language of written speech in the technical field. Therefore, teaching English should include a detailed and thorough study of the grammatical system. Students of technical specialties are willing to study grammar, the specifics of their thinking allows them to perceive information well in the form of tables and diagrams. Students often build their own system of learning, memorizing and using language rules. This analytical approach extends to the study of vocabulary – students build analogies, analyze the composition of a word, and willingly work with a dictionary. However, spontaneous speech, both oral and written, is more difficult for them. Usually, students try to build statements from ready-made blocks of lexemes and grammatical constructions. Their accuracy in the use of words and rules is noticeably higher, however, such selection significantly increases the time to complete the task [5, C. 62].

The understanding of written language increases due to the use of translation in the classroom. Since students tend to analyze, drawing parallels with their native language, understanding the text, as well as mastering grammatical rules, is faster. In mastering highly specialized vocabulary, translation is also necessary. Working with a dictionary is also welcome here, as often a word can have several meanings depending on the industry of use. This further increases the degree of assimilation of the material, since students are often familiar with these terms from the course of other disciplines.

It is worth noting that the grammar-translation method is advisable to use at the initial stages of learning English at a university. At the first stage (the first year of study), it is necessary to provide a solid foundation for further language learning. The level of knowledge of yesterday's students may, firstly, differ significantly, and secondly, often this knowledge is not enough for further study of English for special purposes. Therefore, the first block of training should consist of studying and repeating grammatical rules, and here it is the grammatical-translation method that has the greatest productivity. Relying on translation allows you to learn the rules based on your native language, and closes gaps in vocabulary knowledge. In the future, the speed of perception of information in English gradually increases, which allows us to move on to narrower topics in the next stages [6].

In the subsequent stages, students already have a sufficient vocabulary and a good knowledge of grammar. Therefore, the use of innovative pedagogical technologies is possible here. One of them is the project method. This method embodies both the ideas of the competence approach and the opportunity to show creative thinking. The preparation of projects helps to improve students' spoken language, to study thematic vocabulary and grammar in more detail. Among other things, students learn to plan work independently, work in a team and assign responsibilities. As a rule, working with projects is well accepted by students. The use of ICT in the preparation of an accompanying presentation also increases the motivation of students to complete the task. It is worth noting that this method can be used at any stage of teaching a foreign language at a university. The difference will be in the topic of the project and the level of requirements [7, C.36-37].

Another method, based also on the principles of the competence approach, is the "case study" technology. This method consists in analyzing and discussing the current situation in English. [8, C.110]. This technique requires detailed training on the part of both the teacher and the students. It is necessary to discuss the topic of the meeting in advance, prepare a glossary, and useful expressions. Do not forget that students of technical fields prefer to build speech from ready-made grammatical and lexical blocks, so you definitely need to give time to prepare. This way of working requires great erudition and pedagogical skills from the teacher, because it is not so much the content of the lesson that is important here, as the direction of the students' activities. This method is most effectively used at the third, final stage of English language teaching at a university. As a rule, by this point, students possess a sufficient amount of knowledge both on the topic of their field and about the world as a whole [9, pp.42-45].

Another way to practice oral speech is the method of debate. This method can also be used in the final stages of language learning. It is advisable to put such a lesson as the final one in the module. This will help to consolidate the grammatical and lexical material that has been passed. The didactic goals of the method are to teach spontaneous speech, the ability to express one's point of view in English, to argue and defend it, as well as to work in a team and ask questions [10, C. 82].

In conclusion, it should be noted that the greatest effectiveness of teaching English at a technical university was achieved by combining the traditional grammatical and translation method and new pedagogical technologies such as debates, project-based learning, and case studies. The traditional method provides

a sufficient knowledge base for innovative technologies. They, in turn, help speech development in non-standard situations and increase students' motivation to study. In general, by the end of the English language course at the university, the level of proficiency required by the standards for future technical specialists is achieved.

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